

The Influence of Product Quality, Promotion and Location on Consumer Purchasing Decisions at The Dikit Lagi Coffee Shop

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to determine the effect of product quality, promotion and location on consumer purchasing decisions at Kedai Dikit Lagi Kopi. The research method is quantitative, primary data source by distributing questions using a questionnaire. Determination of the sample of this study using nonprobability sampling techniques and purposive sampling methods and obtained 100 consumer respondents at Kedai Dikit Lagi Kopi. Data was measured using a Likert scale and analyzed by multiple linear regression. Based on the results of the study that product quality has a positive effect on purchasing decisions, promotional variables have no positive effect on purchasing decisions, and location variables have a positive effect on purchasing decisions. Product quality, promotion, and location together (simultaneously) influence purchasing decisions by 42.3% while the rest is influenced by other factors outside this study.

KEYWORDS: Product Quality, Promotion; Location, Purchase Decision.

I. INTRODUCTION

Currently there are a lot of coffee products popping up, making consumers more selective in choosing the products they will buy. Based on Toffin's research, the number of coffee shops in Indonesia in August 2019 has reached more than 2.950 outlets (Fatmarani, 2022). The coffee shop business in Indonesia continues to experience growth in various places, ranging from urban areas to remote villages which currently have reached 10.000 coffee shops and are predicted to continue to grow from year to year with total revenue from the coffee shop business sector reaching 4.16 billion annually (Putra, 2018). The increase and growth of the coffee shop business is inseparable from the increasing number of Indonesians who consume coffee.

The development of the coffee industry is also highly supported in Indonesia. This is evidenced by the response of the Coordinating Ministry for Economic Affairs, which welcomes collaboration between Indonesian coffee industry players and the government in encouraging the growth of the coffee industry in Indonesia. The government appreciates the commitment of Indonesian coffee industry players to continue to encourage the growth of the Indonesian coffee industry.

The coffee industry has a large role in employment in Indonesia, empowering 1,86 million heads of farming families and 50 thousand general laborers. In the last 10

years, Indonesia's coffee industry has experienced significant growth of 250%. Currently, Indonesia is the fourth largest coffee producer in the world after Brazil, Vietnam, and Colombia. Indonesia's coffee land area reaches 1,25 million ha with a total production of up to 761 thousand tons per year (Econ, 2021).

Indonesia is the fourth largest coffee bean producer in the world, contributing 9% to global coffee production. The increase in coffee production is influenced by changes in the lifestyle of the Indonesian people who follow the trend of consuming coffee and even make coffee a daily necessity. The need for coffee production encourages the development of an industry that is continuous and leads to a global market. The country's foreign exchange earnings increased by 19,1% as a result of the export of processed national coffee in the form of instant coffee, extracts, essences, and coffee concentrates (Ministry of Industry of the Republic of Indonesia, 2019).

In the last ten years consumption grew by 3,7%, the second highest among coffee producing countries. Meanwhile, per capita consumption is still low at 1.1 kg/year. In addition, according to the Director of PT Riset Perkebunan Nusantara in December 2021, Indonesia's current coffee consumption reached 300,000 tons, with growth reaching 8% (Indonesian Information Portal, 2022).

“The Influence of Product Quality, Promotion and Location on Consumer Purchasing Decisions at The Dikit Lagi Coffee Shop”

The following illustrates the level of coffee consumption in Indonesia from year to year:

Chart 1
Coffee Consumption in Indonesia (2010 – 2021)

Source: International Coffee Organization (ICO), 2022

According to the records of the International Coffee Organization (ICO), coffee consumption in Indonesia in 2019 reached 3.6 million bags, while in 2020 it was 5 million bags. This number increased by 4,04% compared to the previous period which amounted to 4,81 million 60 kg bags. Coffee consumption in Indonesia in 2020 to 2021 is also the highest in the last decade. Furthermore, Indonesia's coffee consumption is one of the largest in the world. Indonesia ranks fifth or below Japan, whose coffee consumption reaches the highest level in the world. 7,39 million 60 kg bags. Meanwhile, Indonesia's coffee production reached 774,6 thousand tons in 2021. This value increased by 2,75% from the previous year which amounted to 753,9 thousand tons (Mahmudan, 2022).

Diagram 1
Purchase Decision Pre-Research Results Diagram

Source: Data processed, 2022

The question in this purchase decision prariset is "whether to choose to spend time drinking coffee at Kedai Dikit Lagi Kopi compared to the coffee shops around it". Based on the results obtained from 30 respondents, it is known that 30% chose to strongly disagree, 27% chose to moderately agree, 24% chose to disagree, 13% chose to agree. And the remaining 6% chose to strongly agree. From the results of this pre-test, it is known that the majority of

respondents answered strongly disagree and moderately agree, which means that this coffee shop is not the main destination of the buyers in spending their time. There are several reasons that may be a factor in causing buyers to assume that way. For this reason, researchers conducted further prariset regarding possible factors, including product quality, promotion, and environment.

Based on this, researchers conducted a prariset to find out how important the quality of Kedai Dikit Lagi Kopi products is for consumers before making a purchase and the results of the prariset can be seen as follows:

Diagram 2
Pre-Research Result of Product Quality of Kedai Dikit Lagi Kopi

Source: Data Processed, 2022

The question in this product quality prariset is "Kedai Kopi Dikit Lagi Kopi products serve coffee with flavors that match consumer expectations". Based on the results obtained from 30 respondents, it is known that 17% or 5 respondents strongly disagreed, 27% or 8 respondents disagreed, 33% or 10 respondents moderately agreed, 10% or 3 respondents agreed, and 13% or 4 respondents strongly agreed. From the results of this prariset, it is known that the majority of respondents answered quite agree and disagree, which means that the quality of the products served by Kedai Dikit Lagi Kopi is not in accordance with consumer expectations. This is also reinforced by the statement of the owner of Kedai Dikit Lagi Kopi in an interview conducted by researchers that consumers tend to compare the quality of Kedai Dikit Lagi Kopi products with other shops.

Based on the results of the prariset, Kedai Dikit Lagi Kopi needs to improve the quality of its products to be able to satisfy the taste desired by consumers in order to compete with coffee shops around it. This is in accordance with the definition given by Kotler & Keller (2016) products are anything that can be offered to the market to satisfy a want or need, including physical goods, services, experiences, events, people, places, property, organizations, information, and ideas. This definition can be concluded that a product is everything that a producer offers to consumers to meet their needs and desires and is attached to a product called a product attribute.

Diagram 3
Pre-Research Results of Promotion of Kedai Dikit Lagi Kopi

Source: Data processed 2022.

The question in this promotional prariset is "I often find promotions for Kedai Dikit Lagi Kopi through social media". Based on the results obtained from 30 respondents, it is known that 33% or 10 respondents stated strongly disagree, 43% or 13 respondents stated disagree, 10% or 3 respondents stated quite agree, 7% or 2 respondents stated agree, and 7% or 2 respondents stated strongly agree. From the results of this prariset, it is known that the majority of respondents answered strongly disagree and disagree, which means that Kedai Dikit Lagi Kopi has not run a good promotion to consumers. Supposedly coffee shop promotions can also be done by utilizing social media. This form of promotion can attract the attention of potential customers. This is also done so that Kedai Dikit Lagi Kopi can be better known by the wider community. This is in accordance with the definition of promotion according to Kotler & Armstrong (2018) that promotion refers to activities that communicate the benefits of the product and persuade target customers to purchase the products produced.

Diagram 4
Pre-Research Results of Kedai Dikit Lagi Kopi Location

Source: Data processed 2022.

The question in this location pre-test is "Kedai Dikit Lagi Kopi is in a suitable environment for gathering with relatives". Based on the results obtained from 30 respondents, it is known that 27% or 8 respondents stated strongly disagree, 23% or 7 respondents stated disagree,

27% or 8 respondents stated quite agree, 17% or 5 respondents stated agree, and 7% or 2 respondents stated strongly agree. From the results of this prariset, it is known that the majority of respondents answered strongly disagree and moderately agree, which means that this coffee shop does not meet the criteria for a neighborhood with kinship. One of the reasons is because the location of Kedai Dikit Lagi Kopi is in a crowded and dense place so that the environment seems noisy and uncomfortable. In addition, Kedal Dikit Lagi Kopi is in a crowded environment with other coffee shops so that consumers have many better choices than this coffee shop. In addition, other alternatives can also be done by providing a comfortable atmosphere supported by good music and improving services around locations such as a safe parking area and a wider and more comfortable gathering area.

From the results of the prariset that has been carried out, there are problems in the management of Kedai Dikit Lagi Kopi, especially regarding product quality, location, and location of the coffee shop. This is in accordance with research conducted by Hermawan (2018) which states that product, location, and promotion have both partial and simultaneous effects on consumer purchasing decisions. Based on the explanation above, as well as the results of this prariset, the purpose of this study is to determine the effect of product quality, promotion and location on consumer purchasing decisions at Kedai Dikit Lagi Kopi.

Hypothesis

The hypothesis in the study is based on several previous studies. The results of research Aminudin (2017) and Fahmi (2022) state that product quality affects purchasing decisions. Khoiriyah & Utomo (2021) states that promotion can affect purchasing decisions and in research Hanifaradiz & Satrio (2016) states that promotion partially affects purchasing decisions. The results of research Santoso & Hidayat (2019) state that location can have an effect on purchasing decisions and in research Hasbiyadi et al (2018) state that location partially affects purchasing decisions. Then the hypothesis of this study is as follows:

1. H1 it is suspected that product quality has a positive and significant influence on purchasing decisions
2. H2 it is suspected that promotion has a positive and significant influence on purchasing decisions
3. H3 it is suspected that location has a positive and significant influence on purchasing decisions

II. RESEARCH METHODS

The research method taken by the author is a quantitative research approach. According to Sugiyono (2016) Quantitative research methods can be interpreted as research

“The Influence of Product Quality, Promotion and Location on Consumer Purchasing Decisions at The Dikit Lagi Coffee Shop”

methods that are based on the philosophy of positivism used to research on certain populations or samples, data collection using research instruments, quantitative data analysis with the aim of testing predetermined hypotheses. The data source used in this study is primary data by distributing questionnaires regarding product quality, promotion, and location on consumer purchasing decisions Dikit Lagi Kopi.

This research was conducted at Jl. Dermaga Raya No.322, RT.5/RW.5, Klender, Kec. Duren Sawit, East Jakarta City, Special Capital Region of Jakarta 13470. The time used for this research was eight months from September 2022 to May 2023, which included presentation in the proposal, guidance, until it became a thesis.

The population in this study were all people, both men and women who had bought Dikit Lagi Kopi coffee products, with a sample size of 100 respondents. To determine the sample of this study using nonprobability sampling techniques and purposive sampling method Sugiyono (2016).

Furthermore, the data analysis process in this study is a validity, reliability, classical assumption test consisting of normality, multicollinearity and heteroscedasticity tests. Hypothesis testing which consists of T test, F test and R test. The statistical analysis used is Multiple Liner Regression which is processed with the SPSS program.

III. RESEARCH RESULTS

Based on the results of the research data quality test, it was found that all variables were declared valid. Because it has a rcount value greater than the t table, where the t table in this study with 30 respondents is 0,361. The results of the Cronbach's Alpa coefficient of the product quality instrument (X1), promotion (X2), location (X3) and purchasing decisions (Y) have a Cronbach's Alpa greater than 0.6. These results indicate that the three variables have reliable and reliable questions as a measuring tool for conducting research. After it is known that all the data used in this study are valid and reliable, the data can be processed to be able to test the classical assumptions as follows.

1. Normality Test

The normality test is used to determine whether the sample used comes from a normal population. This test uses the One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test method by comparing Asymptotic Significance (probability) with the significance level. The results of testing the Asymptotic Significance (probability) with the significance level. The results of testing the normality of each variable are shown in the following table:

Table 1. Result of Normality Test

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test		
		Unstandardized Residual
N		100
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	0,0000000
	Std. Deviation	2,79010802
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	0,098
	Positive	0,098
	Negative	-0,079
Test Statistic		0,098
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.018 ^c
a. Test distribution is Normal.		
b. Calculated from data.		
c. Lilliefors Significance Correction.		

Source: SPSS Result, 2023

Based on the table, the output shows that the exat.sig (2-tailed) significance value is 0.18 > 0.05. So in accordance with the basis for making the Kolmogrov-Smirnov normality test decision above, it can be concluded that the data has a normal distribution.

2. Multicollinearity Test

The multicollinearity test aims to test whether one independent variable with another Independent variable in the regression model has a linear correlation Ghozali (2018: 107). In addition, it can be seen from the tolerance value and variance Infiton factor (VIF). Decision making VIF value is less than 10 and if tolerance is more than 0.1 then the variable does not occur multicollinearity, with other independent variables Ghozali (2018). The following are the results of the multicollinearity test conducted using the IBM SPSS version 25 program:

Table 2. Result of Multicollinearity Test

Coefficients ^a			
Model		Collinearity Statistics	
		Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)		
	Product Quality	0,790	1,265
	Promotion	0,902	1,108
	Location	0,796	1,257
a. Dependent Variable: Purchase Decision			

Source; SPSS results, 2023

Based on the table, it is known that the Tolerance value and Varian inflation factor (VIF), as follows:

- a) The Product Quality variable (X1) has a variant inflation factor value of less than 10 (1,265 < 10), with a tolerance value of more than 0.1 (0,790 > 0.1). With these results, it can be interpreted that the Product Quality variable does not occur multicolonierity.

“The Influence of Product Quality, Promotion and Location on Consumer Purchasing Decisions at The Dikit Lagi Coffee Shop”

- b) Promotion variable (X2) the variant inflation factor value is less than 10 ($1,108 < 10$), with a tolerance value of more than 0.1 ($0,902 > 0.1$). With these results, it can be interpreted that the Promotion variable does not occur multicollinearity.
- c) The Location variable (X3) has a variant inflation factor value of less than 10 ($1,257 < 10$), with a tolerance value of more than 0.1 ($0,796 > 0.1$). With these results, it can be interpreted that the Location variable does not occur multicollinearity.

3. Heteroscedasticity Test

Heteroscedasticity is a condition where in the regression model there is an unequal variance from the residuals of one observation to another Prayastama (2017:). Various heteroscedasticity tests, namely the pattern of dots on scatterplots or the spearman correlation coefficient test where this method correlates the independent variable with the Unstandardized Residual value. The following are the results of the heteroscedasticity test conducted using the IBM SPSS version 25 program:

Picture 1. Result of Heteroscedasticity Test

Source: SPSS results, 2023

Based on the picture above, it can be seen that if the points spread above or below and the distribution of data points does not form a pattern, then the pattern means that there is no heteroscedasticity.

4. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

The Regretion equation in this study is to determine how much influence the variables, namely product quality (X1), promotion (X2), and location (X3) have on purchasing decision (Y). The following are the results of multiple Linear regression test carried out with the IBM SPSS version 25 program.

Table 3. Result of Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	6,130	4,147		1,478	0,143
	Product Quality	0,586	0,101	0,507	5,814	0,000
	Promotion	-0,120	0,111	-0,088	-1,077	0,284
	Location	0,182	0,067	0,237	2,723	0,008

a. Dependent Variable: Purchasing Decision

Source: SPSS results, 2023

Based on the results og the data processing table above, the multiple linear regression equation is obtained as follow:

$$Y = 6,130 + 0,586X1 - 0,120X2 + 0,182X3 + e$$

- 1) The regression coefficient value of the product quality variable (X1) is positive at 0.586. This means that if there is an increase in the product quality variable (X1) by 1 unit, the purchase decision will increase by 0,586 units.
- 2) The regression coefficient value of the promotion variable (X2) is -0,120. This means that if there is an increase in the promotion variable (X2) by 1 unit, it will reduce the purchase decision by 0,120 units.
- 3) The regression coefficient value of the location variable (X3) is positive at 0,182. This means that if there is an increase. This means that if there is an increase in the location variable (X3) by 1 unit, the purchase decision will be 0,182 units.

5. T Test (Partial)

The t-test was conducted to partially test the independent variables, namely Product Quality (X1), Promotion (X2) and Location (X3) on the dependent variable (Y) in the form of Purchasing Decisions at Kedai Dikit Lagi Kopi. The test results are: Error rate (a) = 5% Degree of freedom (df) = (n - k) Description: n = Number of samples, n = 100 k = Number of variables used, k = 4 Degree of freedom (df) = (n - k) = 100 - 4 = 96 The t-test table used is 0.05 (96) = 1.660.

Table 4. T Test

Coefficients ^a			
Model		t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	1,478	0,143
	Product Quality	5,814	0,000
	Promotion	-1,077	0,284
	Location	2,723	0,008

The relationship test of the independent variables Product Quality (X1), Promotion (X2), and Location (X3) on the dependent variable Purchasing Decisions (Y) can be seen in the following table:

- a. The tcount value of the Product Quality variable is 5,814 and the ttable value is 1,660, so tcount > ttable ($5,814 > 1,66$) with a significant value ($0 < 0,05$) then H1 is accepted, which means that product quality partially has a significant positive effect on Purchasing Decisions.
- b. The tcount value of the Promotion variable is -1,077 and the ttable value is 1,660, so tcount < ttable ($-1,077 < 1,660$) with a significant value ($0,284 > 0,05$), then

“The Influence of Product Quality, Promotion and Location on Consumer Purchasing Decisions at The Dikit Lagi Coffee Shop”

H2 is rejected, which means that Promotion partially has no effect on Purchasing Decisions.

- c. The tcount value of the Location variable is 2,723 and the ttable value is 1,660, so t count > t table (2,723 > 1,660) with a significant value (0,008 < 0,05) then H3 is accepted, which means that Location partially has a significant positive effect on Purchasing Decisions.

6. F Test (Simultaneous)

The F test is used to determine whether there is a significant effect simultaneously between the independent variable and the dependent variable. With a degree of confidence of 0,05 (Ghozali, 2013). The F-test is used to see together the independent variables, namely Service Quality, Product Quality and Price on the dependent variable, namely Purchasing Decisions. To determine the Ftable value, it is necessary to have a numerator and degree of freedom.

free denominator, with the following formula: df (Numerator) $k - 1$ df (Denominator) $= n - k$ Description: n Number of research samples k Number of independent and dependent variables In this study it is known that the number of samples (n) is 100 and the total number of variables (k) is 4, so that it is obtained: $df_1 = k - 1 = 4 - 1 = 3$ $df_2 = n - k = 100 - 4 = 96$ Then F_{table} 0,05 (3: 96) = 2,70.

Table 5. F Test

ANOVA ^a						
Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Regression	564,354	3	188,118	23,433	.000 ^b
	Residuals	770,686	96	8,028		
	Total	1335,040	99			

a. Dependent Variable: Purchase Decision
 b. Predictors: (Constant), Location, Promotion, Product Quality

Source: SPSS results, 2023

In Table 5, it can be seen that the results of obtaining Fcount in the F column are 23,433 with a significance level = 0.000 greater than the Ftable value of 2,70, with an error rate of a 5%, or in other words $F_{count} > F_{table}$ (23,433 > 2,70). Based on the hypothesis testing criteria if $F_{count} > F_{table}$ and the significance level (0,000) < 0,05, which means that the variables of Product Quality, Promotion and Location simultaneously have a significant effect on Purchasing Decisions.

7. Determination Coefficient Test

The coefficient of determination used is the Adjusted R square value because it is more reliable in evaluating the regression model. The Adjusted R square value can go up.

Based on table 4.14, it can be seen that the correlation value (Adjusted R Square) is 0,423. Furthermore, to calculate the contribution made by the variables Product Quality (X1), Promotion (X2) and Location (X3) to Purchasing Decisions (Y), we will use the following formula:

$$Kd = R^2 \times 100\% \quad Kd = 0,423 \times 100\% = 42,3\%$$

From the results of these calculations, it shows that Product Quality, Promotion and Location affect Purchasing Decisions together (simultaneously) affect Purchasing Decisions by 42,3%, while the remaining 57,7% is influenced by other factors outside this study.

IV. DISCUSSION

1. The Effect of Product Quality on Purchasing Decisions

The results of the research (H1) that has been carried out show that the effect of product quality on decisions can be seen from the statistical results of the t test for the product quality variable with a t value of 5.814 greater than the t table of 1,660 (5.814 > 1,660) with a significant value of 0,000 smaller than 0,05 and the regression coefficient has a positive value of 0586. This shows that product quality has a significant effect on purchasing decisions or H1 is accepted.

The results of this study are in accordance with the results of research conducted by Pertiwi et al (2016) which states that product quality has a significant effect on purchasing decisions. The results of this study are consistent with the results of research conducted by Santoso and Hidayat (2019) which state that product quality has a partial positive effect on purchasing decisions. Stating that in accordance with research conducted by Fahmi (2022) which states that product quality has an effect on purchasing decisions.

2. The Effect of Promotion on Purchasing Decisions

Promotion is a communication activity carried out by a person or company to the wider community. The goal is to introduce products to the public and influence them to buy and use these products.

The results of the research (H2) that has been done show that the effect of promotion on purchasing decisions can be seen from the statistical results of the t test for the promotion variable with a t value of -1,077 smaller than the t table of 1,660 (-1,077 < 1,660) with a significant value of 0,284 > 0,05 and the regression coefficient has a negative value of -0,120.

This shows that promotion has no effect on purchasing decisions or in other words H2 is rejected. The results of this study are in accordance with the results of research conducted by Hasbiyadi, Mursalim, Suartini, et al (2018) states that this study shows that promotion has a negative effect on purchasing decisions.

3. The Effect of Location on Purchasing Decisions

Location is a place where the company operates and produces goods and services and the selection of a company location determines the success of a business. The results of the research (H3) that has been done show that the effect of location on purchases can be seen from the results of the t test statistics for the location variable with a t value of 2.723 greater than the t table of 1,660 (2,723 > 1660) with a

significant value of 0,008 smaller than 0.05 and the regression coefficient has a positive value of 0,182. This shows that location has a significant effect on purchases or in other words H3 is accepted.

The results of this study are in accordance with the results of research conducted by Harahap (2020) which states that location has an effect on purchasing decisions. The results of this study consistent with the results of research conducted by Santoso and Hidayat (2019) which states that location has a positive effect partially on purchasing decisions.

4. Effect of Product Quality, Promotion and Location on Purchasing Decisions

The results showed that there is an influence of product quality, promotion, location on coffee purchasing decisions at coffee shops again. This is evidenced by the statistical results of Fcount of 23,433 with a significance of 0.000. Because the significance value is less than 0,05 ($0,00 < 0,05$), this study succeeded in proving that "there is a significant effect of product quality, promotion and location on purchasing decisions.

The results of the determination test R^2 in this study obtained a determinant value R^2 of 0,423 which means that the magnitude of the influence of product quality, promotion and location variables on purchasing decisions is 42% and the remaining variables are not included in this study.

The results of this study are in accordance with the results of research conducted by Fitri (2018) The results showed that the marketing mix consisting of product, price, distribution or place, and promotion simultaneously influenced purchasing decisions. The results of this study are consistent with the results of research conducted by Dewi (2018) The results showed that partially and simultaneously the marketing mix (product, price, promotion, and location) influenced the purchasing decisions of Chang Tea consumers in Surabaya.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This study aims to determine the effect of product quality variables (X1), promotion (X2) and location (X3) on purchasing decisions (Y) to find out which is the most dominant among these variables. From the formulation of the problem, the data analysis proposed in the discussion of the previous chapter, therefore several conclusions can be drawn.

1. The product quality variable has a positive effect on consumer purchasing decisions at the Dikit Lagi Coffee Shop.
2. Promotion variables do not have a positive effect on purchasing decisions at the Dikit Lagi Coffee Shop.
3. The location variable has a positive effect on purchasing decisions at the Dikit Lagi Coffee Shop.

4. Product quality, promotion, and location variables have a positive effect on purchasing decisions at the Dikit Lagi Coffee Shop.

VI. ADVICE

a. For Agencies

- 1) It is expected, the Kedai Dikit Lagi Kopi to innovate to create products with superior taste characteristics and different from competitors.
- 2) Hail is expected, the Kedai Dikit Lagi Kopi needs to involve its consumers so as to create closeness between sellers and buyers, therefore to maintain closeness between consumers, shop owners need to be good with consumers such as asking about input for Kedai Dikit Lagi Kopi.
- 3) It is hoped that Kedai Dikit Lagi Kopi needs to create its own competitive advantage, so that consumers decide to make purchases at Kedai Dikit Lagi Kopi.
- 4) It is hoped that the Kedai Dikit Lagi Kopi needs to be considered when consumers come to buy coffee and what flavors consumers like to order that shop owners need to pay attention to so that the products offered to consumers become their first choice.

b. For Future Researchers

From the results of R square, it shows that product quality, promotion and location together (simultaneously) influence purchasing decisions by 42,3%, while the rest is influenced by other factors outside this study. In this case, further research is recommended to examine and examine other factors outside of this study such as service quality variables, price and consumer loyalty.

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“The Influence of Product Quality, Promotion and Location on Consumer Purchasing Decisions at The Dikit Lagi Coffee Shop”

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